

THE FORMED PERCEPTIVE ABILITY OF THE TUTOR AND ITS PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.

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Annotation: In this article about the perceptive ability of the tutor's personality and its significance in the process of students' perception and psychological characteristics are described. The article contains information about the perceptive mechanisms of the tutor's communication, which is shown in the example of the tutor's interaction with the student..

Key words: Perceptual poisoning, treatment, perceptual mechanisms of tutor communication, causal attribution.

The perceptive side of communication is the perception, understanding and evaluation of a person by another person. By understanding another person, a person can more clearly determine the perspective of the activity and communication with the interlocutor.

The successful occurrence of joint activity largely depends on how the participants of the communicative process perceive each other, what ideas each participant has about the other participant. This creates the need to study the perceptive side of communication. The process of mutual perception of people is an integral part of communication, it is the perceptive side of communication. The perception of a person by a person is called "social perception". Initially, this term was used by J. Bruner in 1947, which meant the social determination of perceptual processes. Later, this term began to mean the process of perception of social objects, that is, people, social groups, large social structures.

A person working as a tutor in a higher education organization also shows himself as an active subject, a person who has a close relationship with a student and is directly related to his development process. In the complex of abilities of a tutor, perceptive ability is also of special importance. The role of this skill and competence in his work with each student and his ability to clearly feel the atmosphere of the group opens the door to powerful educational opportunities. In the processes of social education and influencing students, the tutor can perceive the following:

- an individual belonging to his group, that is, a student;
- the group of students and the social situation of the group;
- objects belonging to the student's person which is parents and others.

As the tutor and students perceive each other in the process of communication, the process of attraction may occur, that is, a "feeling of liking"

may appear in relation to the perceived person. Attraction is formed as an emotional attitude of the subject towards the object of perception.

Dialogue participants try to reconstruct each other's inner world in their minds, to understand their feelings and the reasons for their behavior. The tutor must perform a certain task in order to understand the identity of the people with whom he communicates through the external appearance, behavior and behavior of the students, their abilities, intentions, etc. will come.

Well-known psychologist S.L. Rubinstein wrote: "When we interact with people in our daily life, we are guided by the behavior of the document. After all, we extract document information by "reading" the article as if, that is, by "digesting" it, thereby determining the content of the text, which has an aspect of internal experience. This kind of learning happens quickly, because in the process of communicating with people around us, to a certain extent, we could automatically apply the adjective to the verb.

The perceptive aspect of the tutor's communication means that the student's personality is understood and evaluated by him.

Three communication processes involve two people. Create an image of the interlocutor based on the person's appearance and actions. In perceiving each other, the mechanisms are extraordinary actions:

1. Identification is the attempt of the tutor to understand the student's thoughts and ideas by putting himself in the place of the interlocutor, i.e. the student.
2. Empathy is a person's attempt to understand the experiences and feelings of the interlocutor by putting himself in the mind of the interlocutor.
3. Reflection is an attempt to understand how the tutor is perceived and understood by the student.
4. Stereotyping is the use of certain templates by the tutor trying to understand the interlocutor, that is, the student.

Identification (from the Latin "equalization", "exact likeness") is a way of understanding another person by consciously or unconsciously simulating his tariff with the subject's own tariff. The tutor and the students try to put themselves in the other person's shoes in the situations of mutual action and guess about his inner state, intentions, thoughts, inclinations and feelings. For example, a student who is excitedly flipping through a book before an exam, by remembering his student days, begins to experience their mental state in his mind.

Reflection (Latin for "reproduction") is the analysis and reflection of one's own thoughts and experiences, that is, the interlocutor's understanding of how

the interlocutor perceives him. The perception of the tutor by the student can be likened to a reflection in a double mirror. When a person reflects another person, he also reflects himself. If a person has complete, scientifically based information about the people he interacts with, he can interact with them with unerring accuracy. However, the tutor cannot always have such accurate information. Therefore, he is forced to think about the reasons for his behavior. Inventing motives, feelings, aspirations, and thinking to explain the actions of another person is called **causal attribution**. This interpretation of the reason of the student's actions by the tutors complicates the pedagogical treatment in the group.

The phenomenon of causal attribution is also observed during social perception. Causal attribution is the interpretation of the behavior and motives of other people by the subject of social perception. Due to the fact that the tutor does not have detailed information about the perceived student through observation, he looks for the approximate reasons determining his behavior and "attaches" them to the behavior of the object of perception, even if it is wrong. In other words, causal attribution is the attribution of certain causes to events and human behavior. G. Kelly distinguished **personal attribution** (in which the reasons are attached to the object of the action), **object attribution** (the reasons are attached to the object to which the action is directed), and **situational attribution** (in which the reasons are attached to the situation in which the action is taking place).

Causal attribution comes from the Latin cause and attribute. The nature of causal attribution depends on a variety of conditions well studied by psychology. For example, when perceiving a stranger, the information possessed by the subject of perception plays a major role. A.A. In Bodalyev's experiments, students in two groups were shown a photograph of one person. In the first group, this person is classified as a criminal. They were asked to describe him based on his appearance, and the second group was told that this man was a famous scientist. The students described the person who was called a criminal as a cowardly, evil, cruel, cunning person, and the students of the group who was called a scientist were described as kind and wise, a person who sacrifices his life. The same situation occurred when pictures of beautiful people were presented, that is, beautiful people were rated as good, polite, intelligent. Ugly people are considered to be cowardly, mean, and selfish. Therefore, the tutor's information about the object of perception is a serious basis for the formation of misconceptions and subjectivism.

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In general, it is appropriate to conclude that the tutor's perceptive ability is an important psychological factor in influencing the personality of the student during the education process, understanding him, and planning the system of actions in advance.

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